

The Impact of Brand Image and Marketing Mix on Buying Decision for Toyota Calya

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ABSTRACT

Toyota Calya is one of Toyota's product which succeed in achieving high sales volume based on GAIKINDO's data. Toyota Calya sold around 68.038 unit for the year 2017 only. This fantastic sales volume record was indicated to be influenced by the strong brand image of Toyota in the mind of Indonesian consumers and the core elements which built Toyota Calya as a solid offering, includes product, price, place, and promotion. This research is designed to identify the impact of brand image and marketing mix variable on Toyota Calya's buying decision. This quantitative research is conducted on 60 selected responders based on purposive sampling method. The method of analysis used in this research is multiple linear regression. The data analysis result shows that there is significant evidence to conclude that brand image and marketing mix variable has positive impact on Toyota Calya's buying decision. The well known Toyota brand and the easiness to gather relevant information about the product considered as strong contributor on Toyota Calya buying decision.

Keywords-- Brand Image, Marketing Mix, Buying Decision

One of the car brands in the LCGC category that managed to record fantastic sales volume was Toyota. Through the Toyota Calya variant which was launched in August 2016, this 7-seater LCGC from the Toyota manufacturer received a very good reception from the public. Based on data from GAIKINDO, the Toyota Calya was listed as the second best-selling car after the Toyota Avanza, with sales records of 68,038 units in 2017. However, a similar sweet story was not obtained by the twin Toyota Calya products launched simultaneously, namely Daihatsu Siga. GAIKINDO notes that the sales level of Daihatsu Siga in the same period was only 41,538 units. Although it is not a bad result, the sales performance is not in line with the manufacturer's expectations.

Based on the initial interviews with several Toyota Calya consumers found at the large-scale national automotive show, their purchasing decisions were based on consideration of the Toyota brand attached to Toyota Calya products. In addition, they also consider the factors of product features that are balanced with relatively affordable prices, product availability, and various information about the promotion of Toyota Calya products.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's economic growth throughout 2017 shows a pretty good number since 2014 ago. According to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), Indonesia's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or economic growth shows an increase of up to 5.07% in 2017, where this increase is the highest increase since 2014. Indonesia's increasing economic growth certainly affects the purchasing power of the people of Indonesia. The Association of Indonesian Automotive Industries (GAIKINDO) recorded car sales in 2017 reaching 1.079,000 units, an increase of around 1.6% from the previous year. The not-so-significant increase was allegedly due to a decline of around 34% in sedan category car sales and a 26% decline in the 4x4 category. However, GAIKINDO noted that there was a considerable increase in attention by 26% in the Low Cost Green Car (LCGC) category, equivalent to an increase in sales of 230,000 units within one year.

II. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted in the area of Depok City, West Java in the period December 2017 to March 2018. The independent variables in this study were brand image and marketing mix. While the dependent variable in this study is a buying decision. The population in this study were all consumers of Toyota Calya in the Depok City area. While the sample in this study is some consumers of Toyota Calya who have purchased the product through an authorized Toyota dealer in the city of Depok, West Java.

The sample in this study was set at 60 respondents. The basis for determining the number of samples in this study is by referring to the Siddiqui guideline (2013) which states that for research with multiple linear regression analysis methods, it is recommended that each predictor take an estimated observation between 15-20 observations. Consider the upper limit of the estimation, and consider the

variables observed in this study, then the number of samples is set at 20 observations x 3 variables = 60 respondents.

The data needed in this study was collected using a questionnaire instrument that had been tested for validity and reliability. The analytical method used in this study is multiple linear regression which has been tested for its classic assumptions (normality, multicollinearity, and heterocedasticity).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of the characteristics of the respondents studied gave an indication of the characteristics of the target market suitable for Toyota Calya products, namely: men (80%), aged between 31-50 years (51.6%), domiciled in Jakarta and Depok (52.4%), working as a private employee and entrepreneur (60%), having consumption expenses between under IDR 6,000,000 per month. Based on the estimation of respondents' consumption expenditure, estimation of the respondents' income can be estimated assuming expense-to-revenue 30%, then the estimated income of respondents is around Rp.20,000,000 per month.

The brand image variable is perceived well (MS = 3.91) by the respondents studied. The indicator with the highest average value on the variable brand image is knowing the car with the Toyota Calya brand (MS = 4.43). While the indicator with the lowest average value on the brand image variable is the Toyota Calya is a unique car (MS = 3.05).

The marketing mix variable is well perceived (MS = 3.66) by the respondents studied. The indicator with the highest average value in the marketing mix variable is that information about Toyota Calya is easily obtained through various media (MS = 4.02). While the indicator with the lowest average value is the Toyota Calya is an attractive design car (MS = 3.12).

Simultaneously, the brand image variable and marketing mix have an effect of 57.9% on Toyota Calya purchasing decisions (R Square = 0.579), while the remaining variations on the purchase decision variable of 42.1% are explained by other variables not examined. The influence is a significant influence (p-value = 0.000, smaller than the level of significance (α) used, which is 5% (0.05)). The partial test conducted shows that the brand image variable has a significant positive effect on Toyota Calya purchasing decisions (Beta = 1,052). Likewise with marketing mix variables, it also has a significant positive effect on Toyota Calya purchasing decisions (Beta = 0.493).

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of the data analysis performed show enough evidence to conclude that the brand image variable

has a significant positive influence on Toyota Calya purchasing decisions. Thus, the better the Toyota Calya brand image in the minds of potential consumers, the stronger the tendency of potential consumers to purchase Toyota Calya, and vice versa.

The results of data analysis also show enough evidence to conclude that the marketing mix variable has a significant positive influence on Toyota Calya purchasing decisions. Thus, the better consumer perceptions related to the Toyota Calya marketing mix, the stronger the tendency of these potential consumers to purchase Toyota Calya, and vice versa.

The results of the data analysis also show that the Toyota brand that is well known to potential consumers and the ease of finding information related to Toyota Calya products is a major contributor to the strong tendency of potential consumers to purchase Toyota Calya products.

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